

Professional Ethics as Perceived by the Primary School Women Teachers in Madurai District

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Abstract

Character building being the prime aim of education it considered the values significantly and used the educational experiences provided at the institutions for promoting the long cherished values. However, one cannot exaggerate or over blow ethics. Accordingly codes of conducts were evolved and put to practice for achieving good professional ethics. Realization of duties and responsibilities by the teachers, parents, students and policy implementers and educational administrators paying due attention to the ethical practices was an important aspect in the educational endeavors. Practicing good ethics in the field of education is primarily expected from the teachers. Teachers handle various lively problems while dealing with the parents, students. Any un-ethical act or deed or practice by teachers causes great ripples in society and affects many adversely. This calls for proper and to great extent ideal practices by teachers which enable in sustaining the respect, to the teaching community as well as to the educational institutions. Professional practices of teachers always inspired and motivated the students in their own conduct shaping, and remain ethical. Professional ethics as practiced in the educational institutions by the teachers and students reflect the values being nurtured in the process of education. Be it examination system or admission process or parent-teacher interaction or the teacher’s response to the students errors or misconduct etc. always calls for a good professional response from the teachers.

Need for the Study

Ethics means a code of conduct that directs an individual in dealing with others. Professional Ethics is a form of skill that examines ethical moralities and honesty or ethical problems that can arise in a professional environment. It deals with matters regarding morals, principles, duties and corporate governance applicable to institutions and its employees, parents, and students. Henry Kravis had to say about professional ethics: “If you don’t have integrity, you have nothing. You can’t buy accountability. You can have all the money in the world, but if you are not a moral and ethical person, you really have nothing.” Ethics are also related to the core of management practices such as human resource management, accounting information, production, sales and marketing, intellectual property knowledge and skill, international and economic systems. In the corporate world, the organization’s culture sets standards

for shaping the difference between good or bad, right or wrong and fair or unfair. This quote by Albert Einstein says it all: “Relativity applies to physics, not ethics.” The point is that it is possible to make profits without having to negotiate on ethics. And over and above the factor of correctness associated with ethics, ethical business and its proprietors only serve themselves, their clients and the whole enterprise much better in the final reckoning. Lately, ethical issues in institutions have become more complicated because of the international and diversified nature of many big corporations and because of the difficulty of economic, social, global, political, legal, and administrative regulations and peculiarities. Thus institutions have to decide whether to stick to constant ethical principles or to bend according to domestic standards and culture. It can be aptly summed up in the words of John D. Rockefeller: “I believe that every right implies a responsibility; every opportunity an obligation; every possession a duty.” The scope of the present study is the original contribution in the form of measurement of professional ethics as perceived by primary school teachers in Madurai district, besides the illumination of relationships among the variables and their significant variations. Though the result of the study applies to Madurai district only, there is a possibility to apply the same to other educational districts with certain reservations. It is believed that the outcome of this study will be useful for educational administrators and policy makers. It will have an immediate utility to primary school women teachers to design and develop various their professional activities, teaching strategies for developing professional ethics. Hence need for the present study.

Terms and Definitions

- Professional Ethics -** refers to the core of management practices such as human resource management and intellectual property knowledge and skill.
- Perceived -** refers to the apprehend within the primary school teachers’ mind.
- Primary School Women Teachers -** refers to those who are handling the classes I to V standard in Madurai district.

Variables of the Study

Dependent Variable
Professional Ethics

Independent Variables

1. Domicile : Rural/Urban
2. Family type : Joint/Nuclear
3. Number of intimate friends : Below 3/ 3&above

Objectives of the Study

1. To measure the professional ethics as perceived by primary school women teachers in Madurai district.
2. To find out whether there are significant differences in professional ethics as perceived by the primary school women teachers in Madurai district in terms of select independent variables viz. Domicile, Family Type, School Type, and Number of intimate friends.

Hypotheses of the Study

1. Each of the independent variables involved in this study exerts a significant difference in the professional ethics perceived by primary school teachers.

Methodology – in – Brief

Design: Descriptive,
 Method: Normative,
 Technique: Survey

Sample: A random sample of 250 primary school women teachers from in Madurai district with due representation to the variables viz. Domicile, Family Type, School Type, and Number of intimate friends.

Tools used

The tools used for data collection are as follows:

1. General Information Sheet to be structured by the Investigator.
2. Professional Ethics Scale developed by Champa Masiwal, X.(2012).

Statistical Treatments

1. ‘t’- test for significance of the difference between the means of large independent samples.
2. Significance of Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation.

Analysis and Discussions

The average score of professional ethics among primary school women teachers is found to be 55.88, while the theoretical average is 50. This shows that professional ethics among primary school women teachers is well above the average level. It means that primary school teachers are found aware of professional ethics extensively.

Hypotheses Verification

The statistical measures and results of test of the significance of the difference between the mean scores of professional ethics among primary school women teachers in terms of population variables are presented in Table 1.

Variable	Sub-category	No. of teachers	Mean	Standard deviation	‘ t’ value	Significance at 0.05 level
Domicile	Rural	156	56.38	7.17	1.501	Not Significant
	Urban	94	55.05	6.50		
Family type	Joint	184	54.97	6.49	2.733	Significant
	Nuclear	66	56.49	7.19		
Number of intimate friends	Below 3	83	55.52	6.85	-0.585	Not Significant
	3 & above	167	56.06	7.00		

Professional Ethics and Domicile

The calculated ‘t’ value 1.501 is lower than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance. This shows that there is no significant difference between rural and urban domicile primary school teachers in possession of professional ethics. It can be inferred from the above finding that domicile does not influence on professional ethics among primary school teachers. Hence the hypothesis is rejected.

Professional Ethics and Family type

The calculated 't' value 2.733 is higher than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance. This shows that there is a significant difference between joint family and nuclear family primary school teachers in possession of professional ethics. It can be inferred from the above finding that joint family teachers possess more professional ethics than nuclear family teachers. Hence the hypothesis is accepted.

Professional Ethics and Number of intimate friends

The calculated 't' value -0.585 is lower than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance. This shows that there is no significant difference between intimate friends having below 3 and 3 and above primary school teachers in possession of professional ethics. It can be inferred from the above finding that intimate friends does not influence on professional ethics among primary school teachers. Hence the hypothesis is rejected.

Conclusions

The major conclusions arrived at from the study are listed below:

1. Professional ethics among primary school women teachers is well above the average level.
2. Professional ethics among primary school women teachers is found independent of
 - Domicile
 - Number of intimate friends
3. Professional ethics among primary school women teachers is found dependent of
 - Gender
 - Family type

Educational Implications

Professional ethics are as important as personal ethics. Many reputed well known educational institutions have suffered many destructive effects because the management of the institutions may have lacked professional ethics. In order to have a successful education, it is important to smooth going on teaching profession ethically. However, the term "professional ethics", when correctly interpreted, means standards of behavior of every individual in a teaching profession. Thus, a society that lacks ethical principles is bound to fail sooner or later. The main components of professional ethics are respect and honesty. Since all the teachers are a part of the institutions, they are expected to represent it ethically. This is why, for the most part, teaching people usually speak of "we" or "us" rather than the more personal "I". Professional ethics are also usually known as ethical business practices.

Various commission and committees have stressed their promotion of values, positive attitudes and thereby enhancing job satisfaction. Through the programmes of developing desired values, positive attitudes and a meaningful job satisfaction in teachers. Which may to lead to a successful and prosperous society are essential activities in the hands of the concerned authorities.

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